

Mouse Movement with 3D Chaotic Logistic Maps for Generate Random Numbers

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Since last three decades there are close relationships between chaotic theory and cryptographic theory. Chaotic system behaviors like; highly sensitive to initial states, mix up attribute, deterministic nature and also cannot predict the long term returns, these characteristics help the researchers to enhance security of a cryptography systems, therefore growing number of random numbers generators based on chaotic have been proposed. These proposed generators suffer from limited key space and those based on 1D chaotic map have limited entropy generation capability due to their finite number of Lyapunov exponent (s). In this paper, we propose a random binary sequences generator that produces sequence of bits. General structure of proposed model consists of two parts, first part is mouse device as the nondeterministic source and second part is 3D chaotic system with the coordinates of mouse cursor when movement as the initial seeds, and combines the produced values in algorithmic process. The coordinates of mouse cursor are treated as initial random number with post processing with 3D chaotic maps to increase the randomness and security of the keys. The proposed work has high key space and very long period. Also make obvious that the generated keys possess successful statistical characteristics which is expected of true random binary sequences that are suitable to use in critical cryptography systems, these made by evaluating the results by hardness of 16 tests of NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology).